

SYNTHESIS OF EPIC HISTORY AND SPIRIT OF CHARACTER

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The number of works on historical themes in Uzbek literature, which is included in the treasury of world literature, is growing. In the near future, Uzbek prose will change its character, embracing reality in all its complexity and reflecting it in its own way, in its direction and contradictions. Most importantly, he synthesized the image of epic reality with the image of the psyche of the characters. In other words, the strengthening of the image of the psyche in the epic narrative, that is, the reflection of reality through the analytical depiction of the psyche of the characters, testifies to the growing development of psychodogism in modern Uzbek prose. It should be noted that the natural, unique combination of epic, lyrical and dramatic imagery in this process was due to the enrichment of the techniques and means of revealing the psyche of the characters more deeply, reasonably and convincingly.

The rise of the writer Assad Dilmurod in the field of spiritual images is associated with his deeper analysis and interpretation of the spiritual world of man as a writer and as a person. It is inevitable that a certain situation, a certain behavior and a certain mood will not always be the same in a person's activities. In a number of his works, the artist proved that this confidence is replaced by extraordinary, unpredictable situations and actions. At first glance, such cardinal changes in the human psyche seem to contradict the logic of the characters, but a thorough artistic analysis of their inner world, all the contradictions in the psyche leaves no room for the above-mentioned paradox, because the image of the psyche serves as evidence. As you know, writing a historical work has its own difficulties. Especially famous scientists, such as Abu Raikhan Beruni, Pahlavon Muhammad, Amir Temur, Sultan Hussein Baikaro, bear great responsibility for the life and work of the commanders before the creator, the historical and political environment in which they lived. , and, in general, scientific works they are created. requires a lot of imagination. "Pahlavon Muhammad" Assad Dilmurod is somewhat imperfect in its composition due to the multifaceted conflict and its focus on the contradictions between a number of his characters. But if you look closely, it is easy to see that interpersonal contradictions in it are expressed through a variety of mental images. Comparing the psyche of the characters in certain contradictions, that is, using the parallelism of images to describe the struggle between them, the writer Pahlavon Muhammad and other works try to clearly and convincingly reveal the

heroes. Naturally, in this way, the main character is the main character, and the events of the work are often evaluated through the eyes of the characters. The main character has a complex character, he assesses each event or person through his own thoughts, through psychological analysis. For this reason, from the very first pages of the work, the writer turns to memory, which has risen to the level of the favorite method of depicting his psyche. This protagonist analyzes the past, every step he takes, and the people he knows, he knows, with whom he communicates. At the same time, this common thought process allows characters to enter the plot one at a time